

Proudly organized by

International Invention, Innovation And Design Competition 2024

— GUIDEBOOK

Hybrid Mode
i3DC 2nd Edition

<https://i3dc.my/>

<https://t.me/i3dcsupport>

digitalevents.secretariat@gmail.com

<https://t.me/digit360hq>

<https://registro.i3dc.my/>

ABOUT **US**

Sustainable TVET Initiative Through Innovation

International Invention, Innovation And Design Competition 2024 2nd Edition (i3DC) is organized by Kolej Vokasional Tanah Merah, in collaboration with DIGIT360 – UiTM Startup Company, Universiti Teknologi MARA Kelantan Branch, Bahagian Pendidikan dan Latihan Teknikal Vokasional and Zon Kelantan – Zon Terengganu (KELTER).

Cawangan Kelantan

I3DC DATE & TIMELINE

Sustainable TVET Initiative Through Innovation

- **Competition Period**
1 January 2024 – 17 March 2024
- **Registration and Payment Deadline**
17 March 2024
- **Judging (Online)**
04 April 2024 – 10 April 2024
- **Judging (Face-to-Face)**
21 April 2024, Kolej Vokasional Tanah Merah, Kelantan, Malaysia
- **Result and Award Ceremony (Online)**
21 April 2024
- **Result and Award Ceremony (Face-to-Face)**
21 April 2024

choose your category

PROFESSIONAL

- Academician
- Practitioners
- eCertificate
- 1 Unit of Medal

International; USD 100

RM 100.00

TERTIARY

- University Student
- Kolej Vokasional Student
- eCertificate
- 1 Unit of Medal

International; USD 50

RM 80.00

PRIMARY & SECONDARY

- Junior Innovator = Primary
- Young Innovator = Secondary
- eCertificate
- PAJSK
- Medal available for purchase

Free

I3DC CATEGORY ONLINE

choose your category

PROFESSIONAL

- Academician
- Practitioners
- eCertificate
- 1 Unit of Medal

International; USD 100

RM200.00

TERTIARY

- University Student
- Kolej Vokasional Student
- eCertificate
- 1 Unit of Medal

International; USD 50

RM150.00

I3DC **CATEGORY** FACE-TO-FACE

SCHOOL

Authorization Letter

I3DC 2ND EDITION

All project that participate in Junior Innovator and Young Innovator are required to attached an official school authorization letter using your official school letterhead.

Failure to submit the authorization letter may resulted in disqualification of the participation.

https://i3dc.my/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/School-Authorization-Letter_ENG_i3dc2024.doc

Bahasa Melayu

https://i3dc.my/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/Surat_Kebenaran_Sekolah_i3dc2024.doc

English

HOW TO REGISTER

Online Mode

Step 1

- Register new account at <https://registro.i3dc.my>

Step 2

- Login using email (username) and password.

Step 3

- Click 'New Project' to create new submission.
- Submit

Step 4

- New project will be available at dashboard.
- Click 'Pay Now' to confirm the payment.
- For primary and secondary school, you may skip this step.

Step 8 (Optional)

- Optional – you may submit additional documents if necessary – such as copyright, certs, patent, testimony, etc.
- Upload to Google Drive and set permission to 'Anyone can View'

Step 5

- Prepare presentation video.
- Maximum duration is 6 minutes 30 seconds.

Step 6

- Upload video to your YouTube channel.
- Set permission to either Public or unlisted.

Step 7

- Click 'Upload Video' in Registro and paste the YouTube Video URL.
- Submit

HOW TO REGISTER

Face To Face Mode

Step 1

- Register new account at <https://registro.i3dc.my>

Step 2

- Login using email (username) and password.

Step 3

- Click 'New Project' to create new submission.
- Submit

Step 4

- New project will be available at dashboard.
- Click 'Pay Now' to confirm the payment.

Step 5

- Present your innovation face to face at Kolej Vokasional Tanah Merah, Kelantan, Malaysia

RULES AND REGULATION

I3DC 2ND EDITION

NUMBER OF MEMBERS

#RULES 1

Maximum of 8 members per project including teacher/advisors.

PROJECT LEADER

#RULES 2

Junior Innovator, Young Innovator and Tertiary MUST BE LED by an active students. Failure to comply may resulted with disqualification of the participation.

VIDEO DURATION

#RULES 3

Presentation video should be within 4 minutes to a maximum of 6 minutes 30 seconds. Participant must introduce themselves in the opening of the presentation video.

YOUTUBE

#RULES 4

All video must be uploaded to your own YouTube Channel. Please set the video permission to either *Unlisted* or *Public*.

VIDEO VALIDITY

#RULES 5

Date of presentation video **MUST BE WITHIN** the duration of the event (1st January 2024 to 31st March 2024). Any video submitted with previous date will not be consider for the Best Video Award.

PAYMENT & RESULT

#RULES 6

All payment is non-refundable.
All result is non-negotiable.

VIDEO CONTENT

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Innovation and Creativity:

- The award-winning invention should showcase a high level of innovation and creativity. It should demonstrate a unique and inventive solution to a problem or a groundbreaking improvement upon existing technologies.

Significance and Impact:

- The invention should have significant potential for impact and contribute to advancements in its respective field or industry. It should address a critical need, solve a pressing problem, or offer substantial improvements over existing solutions.

Technical Excellence:

- The award recipient should demonstrate technical excellence in the development and implementation of the invention. The invention should showcase a deep understanding of the underlying principles and exhibit exceptional technical skill in its design, functionality, and operation.

Practical Applicability:

- The invention should have practical applicability and demonstrate the potential for real-world implementation. It should possess the necessary features, scalability, and adaptability to be effectively deployed in relevant contexts.

VIDEO CONTENT

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Market Potential and Commercial Viability:

- The award-winning invention should exhibit market potential and commercial viability. It should demonstrate potential demand, marketability, and feasibility for commercialization. Factors such as market analysis, business models, and potential partnerships or investment opportunities may be considered.

Scientific Rigor:

- The invention should be grounded in sound scientific principles and methodologies. It should demonstrate rigorous research, experimentation, and evidence-based approaches in its development and validation.

Intellectual Property Protection:

- The inventor should have taken appropriate measures to protect their intellectual property rights. Documentation and evidence of patent filings, copyrights, or other relevant intellectual property protection should be provided.

Presentation and Communication:

- The quality of the presentation and communication of the invention is crucial. The award recipient should effectively and compellingly communicate the value, impact, and potential of their invention through clear and engaging presentations, documentation, and visual aids.

VIDEO CONTENT

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Ethical Considerations:

- The invention should adhere to ethical standards and considerations. It should not involve any illegal or harmful activities and should align with principles of social responsibility and sustainability.

Originality and Uniqueness:

- The award-winning invention should exhibit originality and uniqueness. It should differentiate itself from existing solutions or demonstrate significant improvements upon previous inventions.

I3DC POSTER

I3DC 2ND EDITION

INTERNATIONAL INVENTION, INNOVATION & DESIGN COMPETITION (i3DC) 2024

"Sustainable TVET Initiative Through Innovation"

Greetings and best wishes from
Kolej Vokasional Tanah Merah

Invention, Innovation and Design Competition (i3DC) 2024 organised by Kolej Vokasional Tanah Merah and cooperation with UiTM Cawangan Kelantan and Digit360 Sdn. Bhd. The focus of i3DC is aligned with the new National Policy on Science, Technology & Innovation (NPSTI) describes an agenda to advance Malaysia towards a more competitive and competent nation built upon strong STI foundations.

With this year's theme "Invention, Innovation, & Design for Educational Sustainability" aims to showcase investable social innovations that will benefit the society and impact the community and nation.

PARTICIPANTS CATEGORY

Maximum 8 participants for each entry

<p>Professional RM100 (Online) / RM200 (F2F) • Academician • Industry International- USD 5200</p>	<p>Tertiary RM80 (Online) / RM150(F2F) • KV students • University students International- USD 350</p>	<p>Primary & Secondary RM 0 • Young Innovator- Secondary school • Junior Innovator- Primary school Local students ONLY</p>
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IMPORTANT DATES

Competition Period: 1 January - 17 March 2024
Registration and Payment Deadline: 17 March 2024
Judging: 4 April - 10 April 2024
Results & Award Ceremony: 21 April 2024

- Mode: Virtual Presence or F2F
- Project Target: 200+ Potential Projects
- Juries: 100+ Juries

COME & JOIN US!

FOR MORE INFO REGISTRATION TELEGRAM SUPPORT GROUP

<https://i3dc.my/>

<https://registro.i3dc.my>

<https://t.me/i3dcsupport>

UiTM di hatiku

I3DC PAJSK

I3DC 2ND EDITION

<https://i3dc.my/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/i3DC2024-BPLTV.pdf>

KEMENTERIAN PENDIDIKAN MALAYSIA
(Ministry of Education Malaysia)
BAHAGIAN PENDIDIKAN DAN LATIHAN TEKNIKAL VOKASIONAL
(TECHNICAL VOCATIONAL EDUCATION AND TRAINING DIVISION)
ARAS 5 & 6, BLOK E14, KOMPLEKS E,
(Level 5 & 6, Block E14, Parcel E.)
PUSAT Pentadbiran Kerajaan Persekutuan
(Federal Government Administrative Centre)
62604 PUTRAJAYA

Telefon : 03 - 8884 5154
Faks : 03 - 8884 5047
Laman Web : <http://www.moe.gov.my>
<http://bpltv.moe.gov.my>

Ruj. Kami : KPM.600-4/4/8 JLD1 (56)
Tarikh : 19 Disember 2023

Tindakan K2le
Pn Tan Soler
J.P.

Pengarah
Kolej Vokasional Tanah Merah
KM 3, Jalan Tanah Merah-Machang
17500 Tanah Merah
Kelantan

Tuan,

PENGANJURAN PERTANDINGAN *INTERNATIONAL INVENTION INNOVATION AND DESIGN COMPETITION 2024 (I3DC)*

Dengan hormatnya, perkara di atas adalah dirujuk dan surat tuan KVTM.100-12/1/1(03) bertarikh 10 Disember 2023 adalah berkaitan.

2. Sukacita dimaklumkan bahawa Bahagian ini sangat mengalu-alukan usaha pihak tuan menganjurkan pertandingan ini bagi mengetengahkan inovasi yang dihasilkan oleh murid dan guru serta memupuk budaya inovasi dan kreativiti dalam kalangan warga Kementerian Pendidikan Malaysia (KPM).

3. Sehubungan dengan itu, Bahagian ini **tiada halangan** untuk pihak tuan menganjurkan pertandingan tersebut di atas seperti ketetapan berikut:

Nama Aktiviti : Pertandingan *International Innovation and Design Competition 2024*
Tarikh : 01 Januari 2024 hingga 17 Mac 2024
Tempat : Secara hibrid
Anjuran : Kolej Vokasional Tanah Merah

4. Bahagian ini berharap pihak tuan dapat menjayakan penganjuran kejohanan ini dengan cemerlang dan berjaya mencapai objektif yang ditetapkan di samping sentiasa mematuhi segala peraturan dan garis panduan pelaksanaan aktiviti yang melibatkan murid-murid sekolah di bawah Kementerian Pendidikan Malaysia.

Sekian. Terima kasih.

"MALAYSIA MADANI"

"BERKHIDMAT UNTUK NEGARA"

Saya yang menjalankan amanah,

(Ts. ZULKARNAIN BIN FAUZI K.M.N., P.M.K.)
Pengarah
Bahagian Pendidikan dan Latihan Teknikal Vokasional
Kementerian Pendidikan Malaysia

I3DC

AWARDS

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<https://i3dc.my>

13DC MEDALS

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1 Unit of Medal is given for each PAID project

Additional medal is available for purchase at RM50/medal

Awarding Percentage

- 30% Gold
- 30% Silver
- 40% Bronze

** Based on jury decision, originality of innovation and other rules and/or regulation.

** All decision is final. No appeal will be entertained.

I3DC

Publication

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Publication opportunities is provided for all interested participants. All accepted extended abstract will be published in APS Proceedings and indexed by OpenAire.

1. Download the Extended Abstract Template: [[Download](#)]
2. Prepare your paper based on the Template provided.
3. Complete payment via URL (**RM50 per paper**): <https://toyyibpay.com/APS-Proceedings-Fee>
4. Submit your Extended Abstract to the following URL: <https://academicpress.digit360.com.my/apsp/index.php/publish/>

The submission deadline is 17th March 2024.

THANK YOU FOR YOUR INTEREST

Kolej Vokasional Tanah Merah, Kelantan, Malaysia

+60 199 396 160

Digitalevents.secretariat@gmail.com

<https://i3dc.my>